

Corrigendum to “Air-sea exchange and gas-particle partitioning of polycyclic aromatic hydrocarbons in the Mediterranean” published in Atmos. Chem. Phys., 14, 8905–8915, 2014

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Figure 2 in Sect. 3.3 on p. 8912 did not show a colour bar and the two maps were erroneously swapped. The correct figure is shown here.

Figure 2. Spatial pattern of fire-related $\text{PM}_{2.5}$ emissions (Global Fire Assimilation System GFASv1.0; Kaiser et al., 2012) for the East Mediterranean ($28\text{--}45^\circ\text{N}/8\text{--}30^\circ\text{E}$), (a) time integral of 10–26 August, (b) time integral of 27 August–12 September 2010, given as sum over each period in mg m^{-2} . Areas with no observed fire activity are displayed in white. Temporal pattern of domain-integrated (c) daily total $\text{PM}_{2.5}$ emissions over 2010 and (d) yearly total $\text{PM}_{2.5}$ emissions over 2003 to 2012. Labelled in red is (c) the period of the Urania cruise (27 August–11 September 2010) (d) and the year 2010.